

Preferred Social Media and Its Relationship to Interpersonal Communication and Classroom Participation

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ABSTRACT

This study deals with the use of social media by secondary school students and its relationship to interpersonal communication and classroom participation. The use of descriptive correlational design in the study gave an appropriate view in finding the most preferred social media that the students use and presented the relationship between the respondents' interpersonal communication and its effect on their classroom participation. The findings revealed that the most preferred social media among students is Facebook wherein there is a high extent of usage of this site in dyadic communication. Further, it was revealed that their classroom participation in both oral and

written are elevated due to their exposure to social media. The students' high extent of Facebook usage in dyadic communication increased their classroom participation.

Keywords: *Social media, Facebook, interpersonal communication, dyadic communication, classroom participation, oral participation, written participation, descriptive correlational design, secondary school students*

INTRODUCTION

The study claims that students, regardless of preferred social media, generally chose dyadic interpersonal communication and significantly increased their classroom participation in oral and written forms due to their extensive social media usage.

It is observed that social media use is evident in secondary school students. Abi (2015) upholds that modern-day classrooms allow students to bring these technologies and use them to accomplish their day-to-day goals. In this scenario, Boyd and Ellison (2007), stated that social media sites such as Facebook, Twitter, and Myspace to create and sustain relationships with others. Teenagers and young adults have embraced these sites to connect with peers, share information, reinvent their personalities, and showcase their social lives (Boyd, 2010). Barua (2012) emphasizes that one of the most important advantages is the online sharing of knowledge and information. This online sharing of information also promotes the increase of communication skills among the learners of educational institutions.

As a consequence, it is difficult to ignore that there must be a mostly preferred Social Networking Site among high school students that they use in socializing and communicating. Also, an understanding of the extent of social media in interpersonal communication specifically dyadic, group, and mass communication is lacking. A relative notion of how this affects the classroom participation skills of students in oral and written class activities made this study more substantial than most similar focusing on social media. In this study, the students preferred social media, and interpersonal communication forms were evaluated to narrow down the most effective social media among the respondents. This study further investigated the extent of these students' social media usage. Finally, a correlation between the extent of social media usage and their class participation was explored.

Statement of the Problem

The study evaluated the most preferred social media of secondary school students and its relationship to interpersonal communication and classroom participation among students.

The study specifically answered the following questions:

1. What is the most preferred social media among High School students?
2. What is the extent of social media use in interpersonal communication on the following:
 - a. Dyadic communication
 - b. Group communication, and
 - c. Mass communication?

3. What is the extent of class participation among students in terms of the following:
 - a. Oral class activities
 - b. Written class activities?
4. Is there a significant relationship between the most preferred social media and the extent of social media use in interpersonal communication and the relationship between the extent of social media use in interpersonal communication and the classroom participation of students?

Significance of the Study

This study focused on the preferred social media and its relationship to the classroom participation of high school students. The results of this study are beneficial to Researchers, ICT Experts/In-charge, Teachers, Students, and School Administrators.

This study will help other researchers as one of their references if they have parallel studies. Through this study, ICT experts/in-charge in schools will have a change of outlook on the use of social media in the schools and in some school-related tasks that may be open to students who will browse social media during class hours within the teacher's supervision. Moreover, teachers' awareness of students' use of social media to improve students' classroom participation will be elevated. This information can serve as the basis for designing teaching-learning strategies and assessment tools to improve instruction. In so doing, students will be aware of the use of social media and their effect on their classroom participation. Furthermore, this study helps school administrators find means of improvement in terms of designing better access for student's maximum participation in class discussions with the help of the advancement of technology and social media.

Review of Related Literature and Studies

Social Media

Social Networking Sites, according to Kaplan and Haenlein (2010), are applications that enable users to connect by creating personal information profiles, inviting friends and colleagues to have access to those profiles, and sending emails and instant messages between each other." The content of these profiles includes information like photos, videos, and personal blogs. Social Networking Sites are platforms where users can create a webpage with personal information to interact with friends both in person and virtually, allowing them to meet people with similar interests (Kuss & Griffiths, 2011).

Boyd and Ellison (2007) also defined social network sites as public web-based services that allow users to develop personal profiles, identify other users ("friends") with whom they have a connection, read and react to postings made by other users on the site, and send and receive messages either publicly or privately. Individuals can be informed about news updates and other users' daily activities. However, users can limit the information they share publicly with others. The impact of the more sophisticated, glamorous, and more "powerful" electronic media (Hasan, 2013) is gradually transforming society, thus making it complex compared to the traditional media system.

It is undeniably true that teachers and school administrators are aware of the impact of media on the 21st century. Not only did the Philippine Civil Service Commission craft rules on its usage but also the Department of Education to regulate its use by teachers and students. Lenhart et al. (2010) reported that about 57% of social network users are aged 18-29. In this regard, Pempek et al. (2009) claim that younger students use Facebook more frequently than older students to keep in touch with friends from High School and their hometown. This was affirmed in the year-end report by House of IT (n.d), which noted that Facebook is the most active social media platform with 26%, followed by Messenger with 23%, while Twitter and Instagram also top the list with 13% and 12%.

Facebook

The most popular social networking sites to date are Facebook (Rainie, Smith, & Duggan, 2013), followed by Twitter (Brenner & Smith, 2013) and LinkedIn (Duggan & Brenner, 2012). Facebook allows users to set up a profile and post updates, links, photos, conversations, and more. Sponcil and Gitimu (2007) reported that 88.5% recognized Facebook as their preferred social media site (p. 7). Wang, Chen, and Liang (2011) reported that students spend roughly 100 minutes per day on Facebook. A study by Pempek, Yermolayeva, and Calvert (2009) showed that students spend an average of 28 minutes daily on Facebook.

In the academic setting, Sheldon (2008) found out that students spend an average of 47 minutes daily on Facebook. This is one of the leading social networking sites, excluding the average time when people spend browsing their phones on other sites, which have no current statistics recorded.

Messenger

KRDS, a Paris-based social media and mobile agency, currently estimates the number of Facebook messenger app users to be between 300 and 550 million. The app's features include text/video chat, group chat, video and voice calls, and photo sharing. Researchers could use these features during online data collection

Snapchat

Snapchat is an application for iPhones, iPads, and mobile devices. It allows subscribers to send pictures to other subscribers that expire in one to ten seconds. There are an estimated 100 million daily active users of Snapchat, of which about 70% are women (Smith, 2015). The app's features include photo and video sharing among friends, and 25% of smartphone users in the United Kingdom use it.

Instagram

Instagram is an application owned by Facebook that allows users to take pictures and videos and share them on various social networking platforms. This image-driven platform creates a unique, visually oriented-storytelling opportunity.

Skype

This app and web-based technology are part of Microsoft. It has brought innovative technology to users worldwide and enables connections among different people to transform their lives. Based on the

monthly active and connected users, it has roughly 299 million users. The features include phone calls, text/video chat, group chat/call, video/voice calls, and photo sharing.

In the study of Adesope R. and Ogan G. (2015), the extent of social media usage among students helps to reduce the barrier to collaboration, skill building, and discovery since they can confidently make forums on school work. Students can not only converse with their classmates but also share media forms such as pictures, videos, or even document files.

The free flow of communication and information in SNS has positive and negative effects. A Study conducted by Sunitha Kuppuswamy and P. B. Shankar Narayan in 2010 clarified that using social media networking takes most of the time of students and redirects it towards non-constructive, often non-ethical, deceptive, and improper activities, for example, texting and chatting with friends for most of the time of the day, time killing by searching for peoples' private life and avoiding their real jobs and studies. Youth, especially students for the most part, utilize social media for time killing and the purpose of happiness; however, it has been found that web use for academic reasons and assignments, including online instructional exercises, online classes, and training material downloading, is a positive step. However, using social media for informal communication is a waste of time and futile. This could depend mainly on how it is used. Submaranian (2017) added that information overload and lack of privacy are two major issues in social media. There is no control over the information that people get through social media. Getting more details before people are ready to receive and process the same for beneficial consumption confuses them.

Interpersonal Communication

Communication is one of the basic needs of our lives. We communicate to satisfy our needs: physical, identity, and social well-being. Those who fail to communicate report negative life satisfaction, early death, lack of identity, and low relationship development (Turnbull, 2010). Interpersonal Communication means using verbal and nonverbal messages to exchange meaning and emotions (mostly in face-to-face communication) between two or more parties. It is spoken and written words with nonverbal cues to develop and maintain relationships with friends and family.

Dyadic communication

Dyadic communication is face-to-face verbal communication between two people involving their mutual ideas, thoughts, behaviors, ideals, likings, and dislikes. Through the tools of computers and cell phones, society has moved from engaging in face-to-face interaction while performing these activities to engaging in endeavors that do not require in-person interaction with others. The capabilities of computers and cell phones have allowed users to develop means to participate in social networking, making the device the mediator of communication between individuals.

SNS can facilitate easy and free communication. However, how people are affected by their capacity to interact with others is interesting and intriguing since it has the capacity of the three types of communication, such as dyadic, group, and mass. This technology provides a virtual community. Eid & Al-Jabri (2016) stated that social media also provides convenient ways of peer-to-peer exchange of knowledge and collaboration. Innovators design Social Networking Sites to promote interaction and to communicate informal and personal experiences.

Group communication

This is interpersonal communication within groups of between 3 and 20 individuals. Groups generally work in a context that is both relational and social. Social networking is a way that helps many people though they belong to a community. Due to its increased popularity, economists and professors are questioning whether students' performance is not affected by how much time is spent on these sites (Choney, 2010). In a study, Pempek, Yermolayeva, and Calvert (2009) discovered that time spent daily on social network sites varies greatly. However, an analysis of the data indicated most participants spent approximately thirty minutes a day socializing, mainly during the evening hours between 9 pm and 12 am. Students spend an average of forty-seven minutes a day on Facebook.

Mass communication

This interpersonal communication deals with how individuals and entities relay information through mass media to large population segments. It is usually understood to relate to print, broadcast, or the internet, as these mediums are used for disseminating information, news, and advertising. Social media will continue to be the favored form of communication among young people. However, according to Submaranian (2017), this shift may affect the ability to communicate in person properly. This is seconded by Mansi Beniwal (2018) in his article *Social Media and its impact on interpersonal communication*. Beniwal asserted that instead of bringing people together, social media can create distance among them. Although people are becoming more social with social media, there has been an inevitable shift in our ways of communication. More and more online interaction has led to reduced face-to-face interaction.

Class Participation

Social media are increasing student engagement outside of the classroom and they are creating new and innovative ways to learn (see Ivala & Gachago, 2012; Bynum, 2011). Student engagement represents the time and effort students invest in their education. DeBell and Chapman (2006) pointed out that adolescents and young adults are the heaviest users of computers and the Internet.

However, the slow adoption of social media for teaching purposes continues to rise each year. The somewhat sluggish integration of social media into teaching may be associated with any number of common concerns about these technologies including privacy, intersections of personal and professional identities, assessment, integration with other campus tools, and variability of institutional support (Tintikane, 2013). Further, as Valetsinos, Kimmons, and French (2013) note, there remains a relative dearth of empirical data about instructor experiences using social media in their teaching.

Blending the real and virtual worlds, inside and outside of the classroom has increased peer-to-peer and academic engagement, especially for first-year students, Mc Carthy (2010). Social networking offers students new ways of researching and learning. His study showed that through the use of this collaborative learning tool, students were able to engage with their peers and develop some sense of belonging within the learning community. Students were able to form academic relationships, freed from the constraints in the classroom and their inhibitions. This is because social networks have removed all the communication and interaction barriers, and now one can communicate his/her perception and thoughts over varied topics.

Nonetheless, privacy and security concerns challenge the use of SNS tools for promoting student collaboration and facilitating engagement (Waycott, Thompson, Sheard, & Clerehan, 2017). Due to the lack of face-to-face interaction and the ability to collaborate with other students who one may not have met physically, they can put students in danger as they may deal with individuals they do not know (Kwon, Park, & Kim, 2014). In addition, SNS exposes them to an enormous amount of data and information, which may be difficult to process and identify the quality levels of the information received (Bright, Kleiser, & Grau, 2015).

Submaranian (2017) also added that social networks have affected our communication, the way we converse, and our writing techniques. The social web has changed the written word in a couple of crucial ways: Writing is more summarized: However, this has allowed for shorter sentences or paragraphs and made way for neglecting correct grammar. Abbreviations are more prevalent: People who communicate via social media or text message aren't necessarily misspelling things incorrectly; they use a new language entirely.

Educators' understanding of how to work with, instead of against, these social media tools is the key to enhancing students' writing skills. According to Emily Shaver in her study *Effects of Social Media in Writing Skills*, if social media is not used in a classroom, then it may not allow students who are weaker in grammar to analyze writing skills differently. She further explained that it is an excellent way for students to keep track of their writing so that they can assess their improvement over time. Social media provide an advantage to people in comparison to writing with pen and paper. Social media offers the advantage of being accessible from multiple locations, which reduces the possibility of writing being misplaced or lost. Social media can help writing skills because it allows students to access their writing more efficiently and assess their writing over time and in one place.

According to Richardson and Pacopella (2009), it has been forty years since the teaching of writing in schools has had a major shift. It may be with the invention of Facebook, YouTube, blogs, and more that the new writing pedagogy is upon us and is redirecting our writing of today. The changing of writing is understood by the National Council of Teachers of English, which published "new literacies" for the readers and writers of the 21st century. The "new literacies" share reading and writing information for global access and build student relationships among peers to work collaboratively. Facebook is a website that has gained a significant amount of attention and research yields its potential to enhance writing skills. When students can connect through social media to improve their writing skills, they are connected in a way that they feel is relatable to their world.

Theoretical and Conceptual Framework

Media System Dependency Theory combined with Gratification Theory provides the theoretical framework of the study.

The study is based on the Media System Dependency theory by De Fleur (Baran & Davis 2000). The theory stresses that people's dependence on media grows with industrialization, which is related to advances in communication technology and changes in family and social relationships that drive people to the media as sources of information and entertainment. The theory of De Fleur(1976) is vital in answering the problem of the study on the extent of social media use.

De Fleur’s (1976) Media Dependency also stresses how people adapt to the changes brought by new media. Thus, social interactions are seen less in a face-to-face encounter but more engagement in online communication.

Regarding social media and social networking sites as crucial variables of this study, this study further adopted the Uses and Gratification Theory. This theory, propounded by Katz (1970), focuses on how people use media to satisfy their needs. An outcome of Abraham Maslow's hierarchy *of Needs* propounds the fact that people choose what they want to see or read, and the different media compete to satisfy each individual’s needs.

In the hierarchy of needs, there are five levels in the form of a pyramid, with the basic needs such as food and clothing at the base and the higher-order needs climbing up the pyramid. The fulfillment of each lower-level need leads to the individual's looking to satisfy the next level of need until he reaches the superior-most need of self-actualization. The Uses and Gratifications Approach emphasizes that people use media for varied purposes. As media users become increasingly confronted with choices, this approach should direct our attention to the audience. In general, researchers have found four kinds of gratifications: (1) Information - we want to find out about society and the world- we want to satisfy our curiosity. This would fit the news and documentaries, which both give us a sense that we are learning about the world. (2) Personal Identity - We may watch television to look for models for our behavior. For example, we may identify with characters that we see in soap operas. The characters help us to decide how we feel about ourselves, and if we agree with their actions and they succeed, we feel better about ourselves. (3) Integration and Social Interaction - We use the media to learn more about other people’s circumstances. (4) Entertainment - sometimes we use the media for enjoyment, relaxation, or to fill time.

The gratification theory is useful in explaining several reasons why people use social media in various contexts. Their behavior can be the leading factor onto which they resort to using SNS in communication or information, and this is where the second and third statements of the study are anchored. This theory further postulates that people are attracted to a medium if it satisfies their needs. Thus, users can make intentional decisions about what activities to perform within a social media network. This theory has been mostly tailored to investigate students’ motivations, behaviors, and experiences on SNSs for educational purposes.

Conceptual Framework

Figure1. Schematic diagram of the conceptual framework of the study

Definition of Terms

The following terms are defined conceptually and operationally to provide a clear understanding of their usage in the study:

Class Participation is the extent to which the students involve themselves in a class, course, etc. This concerns how well they improve in the different aspects enumerated below on the SNS they use.

Dyadic Communication. A type of communication that involves two persons sharing their ideas, thoughts, likes, and dislikes, and all queries and answers with a certain topic.

Group Communication is an extension of interpersonal communication in which more than two individuals exchange thoughts, ideas, feelings, likes, and dislikes.

Interpersonal Communication. The process by which people exchange information, feelings, and meaning. This specifies the type of communication while using SNS.

Mass Communication is communication to a large segment of the population at the same time, usually through many mediums, such as social networking sites, radio, television, and others.

Oral Communication skills. The ability to gather and disseminate information through spoken words.

Social Media. These are the forms of media that deliver all kinds of electronic services. This is the tool used by the respondents in their interpersonal and class participation.

Social Networking Sites. These sites refer to the public web-based services that allow users to develop personal profiles and identities, read and react to postings, and send and receive messages. This is a variable in the study measuring the respondents' frequently used social media platforms.

Written Communication skills. The ability to convey information by composing clear, concise, and error-free messages.

METHODS

Research Design

This study used a descriptive correlational design in which information about social media usage was collected without making any changes to the study subjects. The descriptive method is used to create a picture of the current state of affairs of students towards social media, and would allow the development of questions for further study. Through the descriptive design, the researcher got the current state of affairs of students on social media, specifically dealing with their most preferred social media in the first objective. Second, its descriptive design was also used in the extent of social media use in students' interpersonal communication. The use of descriptive design was to describe the extent of class participation of students in terms of oral and written class activities. Moreover, since descriptive design does not assess the relationship among variables, the researcher paired it with a correlational design. The Correlational design gave the researcher the avenue to determine the relationship among the variables of the study and point out the life events of the respondents. This was used in determining the significant relationship between the

most preferred social media and the extent of social media use in interpersonal communication and classroom participation of students.

Research Environment

The study was conducted in eight schools within Southern Leyte that covered public (National High School and Technical Vocational High School) and private (Religious and Non-religious) schools. The locale of the study were the following schools: Paku National High School and Sogod National High School represented the public national high schools; Bontoc National High School and Liloan National Technical Vocational School were the representative schools of public technical-vocational schools. Moreover, Saint Thomas Aquinas College and Dr. Rath Memorial Foundation Institute Incorporated were private sectarian schools. Libagon Academy and Jose K. Demeterio Memorial Foundation Incorporated were private non-sectarian schools. All identified study locales are within the Division of Southern Leyte.

Research Respondents and Sampling Procedure

The respondents of the study were bonafide high school students in both public and private schools which represented the general perception of secondary students towards social media usage. The schools were selected through purposive sampling. The students were selected through a stratified random sampling procedure wherein the researcher got 60 junior high school students in each school to represent their total population. Several 60 respondents are the same student count of two class sections in a school. Moreover, purposive sampling was used in determining the schools to be conducted. The purposive sampling helped in getting school representatives in different types of schools. A stratified random sampling procedure was used to identify the respondents of the study. Stratified sampling is a probability sampling technique wherein the researcher divides the entire population into different subgroups or strata, and then randomly selects the final subjects proportionally from the different strata. This was done to make sure that different grade levels in the secondary schools were being represented.

Table 1 shows the population of the identified schools and the distribution of the respondents.

Table 1

Research respondents

Type	School	Population	Respondents taken
(Public)	Paku National High School	860	60
	Sogod National High School	2,820	60
	Bontoc National High School	1,200	60
	Liloan National Tech-Voc School	1,068	60
(Private)	Saint Thomas Aquinas College	750	60
	Dr. Rath Memorial Institute Foundation Inc.	429	60
	Libagon Academy	585	60

MACI -JKD	386	60
Total	8,098	480

Research Instrument

The research instrument used in this study was a researcher-made questionnaire which is composed of four parts. Part I solicits information about the respondents' profile (optional), such as name, school, and grade level. The second part focused on the most preferred social media of the students. The third part of the questionnaire was adapted from Adesope and Ogan (2015) and emphasized the extent of social media use in the interpersonal communication of the respondents, whether dyadic, group, or mass. Lastly, Part IV was adapted from Drusell's (2012) Social Networking and Interpersonal Communication and Conflict Resolution Skills among College Freshmen and Belal's (2014) *Influence of Digital Social Media in Writing and Speaking*. This deals with the level of class participation among students in both oral and written communication. Oral and written communication comprises five (5) questions, respectively, using a frequency scale.

Data Gathering Procedure

Preliminary preparations were done before the conduct of the study. These include getting permits from the Schools Division Superintendent, the District Supervisor, and the school principal of the eight identified schools through a request letter to conduct the study with an attached approved permit to conduct clearance.

As soon as the researcher was permitted to conduct the study on the identified schools, he asked for the assistance of two English subject teachers in every school during the distribution of the research questionnaires to the student respondents. The researcher made it sure that there would be sixty (60) student respondents in every school. The selection of student respondents within each class was done through a random sampling procedure.

The conduct and the data collection took place from the second week of February until the last week of March 2019, aligning with the DepEd calendar year 2018-2019.

Questionnaires were collected and categorized from all the identified schools. The data from the collected questionnaires was then entered into a spreadsheet for tabulation. The tabulated data were analyzed with the guidance of a statistician using the SPSS software to ensure accurate and appropriate interpretation of the results.

Data Analysis Procedure

After the data were gathered, careful tabulation in Microsoft Excel was done, while statistical treatment and interpretation were made using the SPSS statistical software. This process was conducted under the guidance of the statistician.

To determine the preferred social networking sites, the frequency with which each site was mentioned by the respondents was counted. These counts were then used to rank the social networking sites from most to least preferred. The results were presented in a table showing the frequency count and percentage for each social networking site.

The preferred interpersonal form of communication was assessed using the Likert scale. Respondents were asked to rate their preference for different forms of communication (dyadic, group, and mass communication) on a scale of 1 to 5, where 1 = Strongly Disagree and 5 = Strongly Agree. Frequency counts and valid percentages were calculated for each category to determine the distribution of preferences. The valid percentages were used to account for any missing responses.

The level of class participation in terms of oral and written was examined through frequency counts and percentages. This allowed for a comparison of the levels of oral and written participation. Lastly, relationships between variables were computed through Spearman's Rho correlation coefficient. The results of the correlation analysis were presented, including the correlation coefficient value (rho) and the associated p-value, which indicates the statistical significance of the relationship. The interpretation of the correlation coefficient considered both its strength and its direction.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Most Preferred Social Media

The social networking sites were listed to determine the students' preferred social networking sites. Table 2 presents the Grade 7 to Grade 11 choices in the SNS enumerated.

Table 2
Most preferred social media among high school students

		Grade Level					Total
		7.00	8.00	9.00	10.00	11.00	
Preferred SNS	Facebook	63	65	81	25	25	259
	Instagram	5	5	0	4	1	15
	Messenger	15	20	14	9	13	71
	Skype	3	1	1	0	0	5
	Snap Chat	0	1	2	0	1	4
	Others	1	3	1	0	3	8
Total		87	95	99	38	43	362

The data reveals a clear preference for Facebook among the surveyed high school students, with 259 frequency counts. This dominance is consistent across most grade levels, although a slight decline is observed in the 10th and 11th grades, suggesting a potential shift in platform preference as students mature. Messenger emerged as the second most popular choice with 71 counts, followed by Instagram with 15. Less popular platforms like Skype (5) and Snapchat (4), along with other unspecified sites (8), had significantly lower usage.

This finding aligns with previous research highlighting Facebook's widespread adoption among teenagers, although its prominence has fluctuated through time. Lantz-Andersson, Vigmo and Bowen (2013) described Facebook as the largest social networking site, facilitating connections, shared interests, and group formation. While Facebook's popularity has seen ebbs and flows, as evidenced by the Pew Research Center's 2015 study showing 71% teen usage (compared to 52% for Instagram and 41% for Snapchat), its enduring presence as a communication tool is undeniable (Lenhart et al., 2015). More recent studies, however, suggest a decline in Facebook usage among teens, with platforms like TikTok and Instagram gaining traction (Anderson & Jiang, 2018). This highlights the dynamic nature of social media preferences and the need for ongoing research including criticisms regarding privacy and data security. Facebook remains a powerful source of information and a potential educational tool, particularly for literacy and writing development (Pilgrim & Bilsoe, 2011). A study by Junco (2015) found that Facebook use is associated with student engagement and academic performance when used for educational purposes.

As educator and researcher Janice Petosky stated, "Teachers have to find out where the students are and work from there. Well, the students are on Facebook (or wherever they are)." This underscores the importance of educators leveraging platforms where students are already engaged. By integrating these platforms into their teaching practices, educators can capitalize on existing student habits and create more engaging learning experiences. This resonates with the broader trend of technology integration in education (Grgurovic, 2010). The combination of face-to-face and online activities, as advocated by Picciano (2009), can be effectively facilitated through social media platforms. Kabilan, Ahmad, and Abidin (2010) further emphasized the value of computer-mediated communication for authentic interaction and positive learning outcomes. A study by Bower et al. (2015) explored the use of social media for collaborative learning and found that it can enhance student interaction and knowledge construction.

The high preference for Messenger (71 counts) suggests its crucial role in students' interpersonal communication. This aligns with Godwin-Jones' (2008) observation that platforms like Facebook can improve communication, interaction, and language learning. The accessibility of Facebook and Messenger, even with limited internet connectivity due to mobile data availability, is a significant factor contributing to their popularity, especially in contexts with limited resources. This accessibility makes these platforms particularly valuable in educational settings where internet access may be inconsistent. A study by Traxter et al. (2012) found that mobile social media use can support informal learning and communication among students.

Table 3.

Extent of social media use in interpersonal communication

	Dyadic communication			Cumulative percent
	Frequency	Percent	Valid percent	
Low	5	1.4	1.4	1.4
Moderate	164	45.3	45.3	46.7
High	177	48.9	48.9	95.6
Very high	16	4.4	4.4	100.0

Total	362	100.0	100.0	
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Group communication

Low	23	6.4	6.4	6.4
Moderate	206	56.9	56.9	63.3
High	119	32.9	32.9	96.1
Very high	14	3.9	3.9	100.0
Total	362	100.0	100.0	

Mass communication

Very Low	1	.3	.3	.3
Low	22	6.1	6.1	6.4
Moderate	165	45.6	45.6	51.9
High	159	43.9	43.9	95.9
Very high	15	4.1	4.1	100.0
Total	362	100.0	100.0	

The data presented in Table 3 shows that students use social media most extensively for dyadic communication (48% rated as "High"). This indicates a preference for one-on-one interactions when using these platforms for academic purposes. While group communication also sees substantial usage (56.9%), it is categorized as "Moderate," suggesting less frequent or less intensive engagement compared to dyadic communication. Mass communication shows the lowest level of usage (45.6%), also rated as "Moderate." This pattern suggests that students primarily leverage social media for direct, personalized interactions related to their studies, rather than broad, broadcast-style communication.

This preference for dyadic communication aligns with the findings of Burke and Kraut (2014), who observed that increased time spent on social networking sites (SNS) correlates with a stronger sense of connection to friends and colleagues. This connection likely facilitates the ease and effectiveness of dyadic communication for academic collaboration. The work of Mbodila, Isong, and Muhandji (2014) further supports this notion, highlighting the role of SNS in fostering student collaboration. The network effect inherent in these platforms allows students to connect and support each other's learning, as noted by Azeta, Eweoya, and Ojumah (2014), who emphasized the positive impact on collaborative learning and class participation. A study by Valenzuela, Park, and Zamith (2009) also found that Facebook use was positively related to bridging social capital, which refers to connections with diverse individuals and access to new information. This suggests that dyadic communication on social media could expose students to different perspectives and resources relevant to their studies.

However, the moderate usage of group and mass communication for academic purposes raises interesting questions. While these forms of communication might not be the primary mode of interaction, they still play a role in students' learning experiences. Group communication, for instance, could be utilized for project discussions, study groups, or sharing resources within a class. Mass communication, although less frequently used, might be employed for announcements, sharing important updates, or disseminating information to a larger student body. Future research could explore the contexts in which group and mass communication are used for academic purposes and the factors that influence their effectiveness.

The existing literature on social media in education presents a mixed picture. While Buzzard et al. (2011) documented positive perceptions of technology in learning, their findings also highlighted the gap between expectations and actual learning outcomes. Similarly, Dyson et al. (2015) found no significant impact of Facebook on student engagement and understanding in a psychology course. These mixed results underscore the complexity of integrating social media into educational settings and the need for careful design and implementation. As Bryson (2014) points out, student engagement has become a prominent area of research, and the influence of social media on engagement is a key aspect to consider. Studies by Croxton (2014) and Shadiev et al. (2014) emphasize the importance of interaction quality and quantity in student learning and development, which social media can potentially facilitate. George (2017) further reinforces the significant role of social media and networks in student engagement. A study by Kuh (2009) found that student engagement, including active learning, collaboration, and interaction with faculty, is a strong predictor of academic success. Social media, when used effectively, can support these aspects of engagement.

Table 4.

Extent of Class Participation in Oral Class Activities

		Frequency	Percent	Valid percent	Cumulative percent
Valid	Never	3	.8	.8	.8
	Sometimes	136	37.6	37.6	38.4
	Often	154	42.5	42.5	80.9
	Very Frequently	61	16.9	16.9	97.8
	Always	8	2.2	2.2	100.0
Total		362	100.0	100.0	

Table 4 presents the extent of participation of students in oral class activities. The data reveals that the majority of students participate in oral class activities "Sometimes" (37.6%) or "Often" (42.5%), suggesting that while oral participation is not absent, consistent and frequent engagement is not the norm for most. Only a small percentage of students "Always" (2.2%) participate, while similar fractions "Never" (0.8%) participate. This distribution aligns with existing research showing that a small group often

dominates classroom discussions (McCroskey & Beatty, 1984), a phenomenon influenced by factors such as personality, communication apprehension, and classroom climate (Daly & McCroskey, 2000).

The findings suggest a link between social media use and enhanced oral competence. Students exposed to social networking sites (SNS) report increased confidence in speaking, particularly when they encounter related information online. This aligns with the common trend of 21st-century learners using social media inside and outside the classroom. Graham (2011) supports this, noting that students improve their social communication skills in English through social media use that improves face-to-face interactions with peers and teachers. This suggests that social media can serve as a bridge, facilitating communication skills that translate to the physical classroom.

The connection between social media and self-confidence is further explored by Clavert (2002), who argues that online communication provides opportunities for self-exploration and identity development, potentially leading to increased confidence in interacting with peers. Giffords (2006) adds that individuals may feel empowered by using social networks to build relationships that offer information, support, and mutual assistance. This sense of empowerment and connection could contribute to increased confidence in oral participation in class. Furthermore, as Wolak, Mitchell, and Finkelhor (2003) suggest, online relationships can serve as stepping stones for teens with social difficulties, helping them develop the confidence to engage in face-to-face interactions. This is particularly relevant to the "Sometimes" and "Often" participants, as social media might provide a safe space to practice and develop communication skills that they then apply in the classroom.

The reasons behind the frequency of oral participation can be multifaceted. Students who "Never" participate might struggle with communication apprehension or lack of confidence. "Sometimes" participants may be more introverted or participate selectively. "Often" participants are likely more comfortable with oral communication, while "Very Frequently" and "Always" participants are likely highly confident and motivated.

It can be inferred that social media use can positively influence oral participation by increasing access to information: Students exposed to relevant information online feel more prepared to contribute to class discussions. Building confidence: Online interactions can foster a sense of empowerment and connection, leading to greater self-assurance in speaking.

Table 5.

Extent of Class Participation in Written Class Activities

		Frequency	Percent	Valid percent	Cumulative percent
Valid	Never	3	.8	.8	.8
	Sometimes	121	33.4	33.4	34.3
	Often	170	47.0	47.0	81.2

Very Frequently	61	16.9	16.9	98.1
Always	7	1.9	1.9	100.0
Total	362	100.0	100.0	

Table 5 shows "Often" (47%) as the most frequent response regarding written class participation, followed by "Sometimes" (33.4%). "Very Frequently" accounts for 16.9%, while "Always" and "Never" are low at 1.9% and 0.8%, respectively. This suggests regular written engagement, but not consistent or extensive participation for most. The "Often" response aligns with the idea that written work is a regular part of the curriculum, but the lower percentages for "Very Frequently" and "Always" indicate that fewer students are consistently engaging in self-initiated or extensive writing.

The high "Often" response rate (170 counts, 47%) suggests that students' written communication is often aided by social networking sites (SNS). Social media, as a free messaging platform, encourages regular writing, whether through personal messages, group chats, or status updates. This constant, albeit often informal, writing practice can contribute to improved writing skills and fluency. As writing and composition improve through consistent practice, social media provides a readily accessible space for such practice.

This observation is supported by a National Literacy Trust study, which found that 57% of surveyed students active on social media enjoy writing more than those less active. These students also felt more confident and perceived themselves as stronger creative writers. This resonates with the "Often" category in Table 5, as regular social media writing likely contributes to a sense of confidence and perceived competence in writing. Further supporting this connection, studies by the Alberta Teachers' Association and the National Literacy Trust which indicate that students active on social media engage in various forms of writing, including short stories, song lyrics, and journaling, further developing their writing skills and fostering a positive attitude towards writing. A study by Ito et al. (2010) found that teens use social media for a variety of writing purposes, including creative expression, communication, and identity exploration.

Fife (2010) highlights Facebook as a powerful tool for enhancing writing skills, suggesting its use as a pedagogical tool rather than simply a distracting platform. He discusses incorporating articles about Facebook use, including profiles, into the classroom, demonstrating how teachers can leverage students' familiarity with social media to enhance literacy practices, particularly writing skills. This aligns with the idea that the "Often" participation in written class activities could be a result of the regular writing practice facilitated by social media, which can then be channeled and refined through classroom instruction. A study by Godwin-Jones (2017) explores the use of social media platforms for collaborative writing projects, suggesting that these platforms can facilitate peer feedback and enhance the writing process.

However, the "Sometimes" (33.4%) responses also warrant consideration. These students may engage in social media writing but struggle to translate that informal practice into consistent academic writing. As discussed previously, factors like writing anxiety, perceived relevance of academic writing tasks, and differing writing styles between social media and academic contexts can influence participation. The "Sometimes" category might represent students who are comfortable with informal writing but lack

the confidence or skills to consistently engage in more formal academic writing. A study by Graham et al. (2012) found that writing anxiety can significantly impact students' writing performance and motivation.

The low "Never" (0.8%) response suggests that most students participate in some form of written activity, even if not consistently. These students might be experiencing significant challenges with writing or be disengaged from the class. The "Very Frequently" (16.9%) and "Always" (1.9%) responses represent students who are highly engaged and confident writers, likely benefiting from both their social media writing practices and their academic writing experiences. Research on writing self-efficacy (Bandura, 1997) suggests that students who believe in their ability to succeed in writing are more likely to engage in writing tasks and persist in the face of challenges. In conclusion, the data suggests a link between social media use and written class participation, with regular informal writing on social media potentially contributing to students' overall writing fluency and confidence.

Table 6.

Relationship between the extent of social media use in interpersonal communication to the extent of class participation

			Extent of Class Participation in Oral Class Activities	Extent of Class Participation in Written Class Activities
Spearman's Rho	Extent of SNS use for Dyad	Correlation	.274**	.272**
		Coefficient		
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000
	Extent of SNS use for Group	Correlation	.236**	.156**
		Coefficient		
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.003
Extent of SNS use for Mass	Correlation	.292**	.293**	
	Coefficient			
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

This table explores the relationship between social media use across different interpersonal communication contexts (dyadic, group, and mass) and class participation (oral and written), employing Spearman's rho. A positive correlation exists between dyadic social media use and both oral ($\rho = .274$) and written ($\rho = .272$) class participation, suggesting that students who frequently engage in one-on-one communication via social media tend to be more active participants in class. This could stem from enhanced communication skills, increased self-expression confidence, or a stronger sense of connection fostered through online interactions. However, correlation doesn't imply causation. Pre-existing personality traits or communication skills might influence social media habits and classroom engagement. Research has also explored the role of social media in relationship maintenance (Cho et al., 2017), suggesting that frequent

online interaction can strengthen interpersonal bonds, which might translate to increased comfort and confidence in classroom settings.

Similarly, social media use for group communication correlates positively with oral ($\rho = .236$) and, more weakly, with written ($\rho = .156$) class participation. Students active in online group interactions appear more likely to participate in class. Online group participation may expose students to diverse viewpoints, encourage the articulation of ideas, and develop collaborative communication skills. The weaker correlation with written participation might be attributed to the informal, rapid communication style often prevalent in online groups, which may not directly translate to formal academic writing. This resonates with research on online learning communities, which has demonstrated the positive impact of active participation on student engagement and learning outcomes. For example, studies have shown that students who actively participate in online discussions develop critical thinking skills, deepen their understanding of course content, and experience a stronger sense of connection with peers (Rovai, 2002), which can contribute to increased class participation. More recent studies have focused on online interactions that promote learning, such as collaborative problem-solving and peer feedback (Hew & Cheung, 2014), highlighting the importance of structured online activities for maximizing learning benefits. This aligns with the idea that online social interaction contributes to meaningful learning and student creativity (McWilliam Dawson, 2007).

The strongest correlations appear between social media use for mass communication and oral ($\rho = .292$) and written ($\rho = .293$) class participation. Students who use social media for broadcasting or engaging with large audiences seem most inclined to participate in class. This could be because they've honed communication skills through online content creation and sharing, are more comfortable with public expression, or have a greater interest in current events and social issues often discussed in class. Uses and gratifications theory (Katz & Blumler, 1974) can help explain this connection. Students using social media to express opinions, share information, or connect with a broad audience might have similar motivations for participating in class. Research on social media's impact on civic engagement has shown that active online discussions can increase political awareness and participation (Valenzuela, Park, & Lee, 2009), potentially leading to greater engagement in classroom discussions on relevant social and political topics. Recent research has also explored the role of social media in facilitating civic engagement among young people (Boulianne, 2015), suggesting that online platforms can provide a space for information sharing, discussion, and mobilization around social and political issues. This also connects to the idea that students learn to view academics from different angles using social media, and teachers should embrace this tool (Ahn, 2011). Rezende (2016) also found that teachers using digital tools effectively improved communication and student engagement.

FINDINGS, CONCLUSION, AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Enumerated hereunder are the findings of the study.

1. Facebook is the most visited Social Networking Site, next is Messenger, followed by Instagram as the third in rank of preference.

2. Students reported a preference for dyadic communication online, which may contribute to the positive correlation observed between dyadic social media use and class participation, suggesting the practice of transferable communication skills.
3. A positive relationship was found between social media use in both oral and written class participation, suggesting that social media exposure may contribute to increased engagement, though causality requires further investigation.
4. A statistically significant relationship exists between social media use in interpersonal communication and classroom participation. Specifically, higher social media engagement, particularly in mass communication, correlates with greater class participation. However, this correlation does not equal causation, and other factors may influence both.

CONCLUSION

The students' high extent of Facebook usage in dyadic and mass communication increased their classroom participation.

RECOMMENDATIONS

To increase the class participation of high school students, the following recommendations, based on the findings of this study are hereby proposed:

1. Given the positive correlation between social media and class participation, particularly in dyadic and mass communication, strategically integrate the most preferred social media into classroom activities to leverage existing student engagement and enhance learning.
2. Focus Monitoring & Evaluation tools on the effectiveness of social media integration for learning, not just usage, and include student input in validation.
3. Use school social media for interactive engagement and dialogue, not just broadcasting information.
4. Guide students in evaluating information from social media sources and developing evidence-based arguments, rather than simply validating or dismissing information. The goal is not just to boost participation, but to cultivate critical thinking and effective communication skills.
5. The rise of visual platforms like Instagram and TikTok might have different implications for class participation compared to text-based platforms like Twitter or Facebook. Future research should investigate these nuances to gain a more comprehensive understanding of the relationship between social media use and class participation. Different platforms may have varying effects on communication skills and classroom engagement.

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